

Bionic Edge Application

Motivation

The users should always be the one in control of his personal data. This is one of the main reasons the BIONIC Edge application was developed. It provides an interface to the AI Chip and provides the user the option to decide if a session should be uploaded to the platform or discarded.

Even though it is always referred to as a mobile app the framework being used for developing the application can create cross platform builds for Android, iOS, or an Electron application for running it on a Windows, Mac OS, or Linux machine.

The AI Chip and the BSN itself do not provide convenient interfaces to the user for configuration and control of the system. The wireless communication with the platform cannot be guaranteed in the use case of the construction workers because there is not always a Wi-Fi network nearby. In that case the EDGE application acts as a bridge between a local Wi-Fi connection to the AI Chip and the remote BIONIC platform.

The Edge application can be downloaded at the Google Play Store:

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=eu.bionic.edge&gl=DE>

UI Overview

The following screenshots shows the login screen and the menu that can be opened by clicking on the Button in the top left corner, or by swiping right on the phone.

Figure 1 - Login Screen and Menu

Login

To log in please click the login button, it will redirect you to the platform to authenticate you as a valid BIONIC user. Please log in that screen with the usernames provided to you by your IT staff:

Once you logged in with your credentials a second screen shows up to ask you for the scopes you want to get acces to. Please check both entries: "profile" and "bsn-data:write" as shown in the second picture.

On successful connection it will redirect you to the home screen. Here's where you can start and stop your data recordings:

On successfully connecting to the AI chip th e followng screen is shown, it allows you to start a new BIONIC data recording session:

If the device cannot connect to the ai chip it shows a warning on the bottom of the screen and the controls for start / stopping a session won't be shown.

In this case:

- Check your wired connections on the ai chip
- Check if the AI chip is powered properly
- Check your Smartwatch – does it show „Connected“?
- Can you access the bionic UI of the device (please open your browser and type the IP address of the AI Chip there – don't forget to set it back to IDLE and close the browser window afterwards)

Starting a Session:

To start a session, click the start button, a dialog will pop up and ask you what you'll be working on in this session:

Once you clicked the START button a new measurement starts, the UI changes to a screen that shows for how long the current session is running already and it offers the user the option to stop measuring by clicking the STOP button:

If the user clicks on the top right corner info symbol a short summary of the current session is being shown in a pop-up message at the bottom of the app:

Stopping a session

To stop a session the user needs to press the **STOP** button, a short questionnaire will be shown where the user should give feedback on his current mood and if he experienced any pain during this session. At the end of the questionnaire the user can decide to upload the data or leave it on the ai chip for uploading it later, or deleting it:

The image displays four sequential screenshots of the BIONIC app's questionnaire process. Each screen features a dark background with a light grey questionnaire box and a bottom navigation bar with 'Home' and 'AI Chip' icons.

- Top Left Screenshot:** Titled 'Questionnaire Form', it asks 'What is your current mood?'. The options are: Very Energetic, Energetic, Neutral, A bit fatigued, and Very fatigued. Buttons for 'BACK' and 'NEXT' are at the bottom.
- Top Right Screenshot:** Also titled 'Questionnaire Form', it asks 'Do you feel any pain / discomfort?'. The options are: No, A bit, and Yes. Buttons for 'BACK' and 'NEXT' are at the bottom.
- Bottom Left Screenshot:** Titled 'Questionnaire Form', it asks 'In what parts of your body do you feel pain / discomfort?'. The options are: Neck, Shoulders, Back, Arms, and Legs. A 'Be careful' indicator is present. Buttons for 'BACK' and 'FINISH' are at the bottom.
- Bottom Right Screenshot:** Titled 'Do you want to upload this session?', it displays session details: Task: Station 1, Start Time: Today at 10:57 AM, End Time: Today at 10:58 AM, Ergonomics: Green, Activity: Green, Fatigue: Green, and Perceived Fatigue: ★★★★★. Buttons for 'DISCARD', 'RESET', and 'UPLOAD' are at the bottom.

- **RESET** button will at any time reset the questionnaire to start all over again
- **NEXT** button steps through the questionnaire
- **DISCARD** button will not upload the data to the platform but keep a local copy for a upload or deletion at a later time
- **UPLOAD** button uploads the data to the platform

AI Chip Session Management

When clicking the ai chip tab or entry in the menu the user gets redirected to a page that shows the currently stored sessions on the ai chip that have not been uploaded yet. There he can decide to upload or delete them

This can be useful if there's no internet connection and the user want to upload the data later.

After uploading a session, a short confirmation message is shown:

If the connection to the ai chip failed a error message is displayed:

Then you should check you AI chip as described in „Starting a Session“